

Tributaries	Bedload (BL)			
	Sample name	>125 μm	<125 μm	Total no of charcoal-BL
Himalayan draining tributaries (HDT)	Aglar R.	0	0	0
	Naro R.	0	50	50
	Bhim R.	2	0	2
	Amlawa R.	2	7	9
	Tons R.	14	5	19
	Giri B.	25	347	372
	Asan R.	1	107	108
	Bata R.	10	76	86
Siwalik draining tributaries (SDT)	SDT 1	0	0	0
	SDT 2	1	45	46
	SDT 3	0	0	0
	SDT 4	0	0	0
	SDT 5	1	8	9
	Peninsular draining tributaries (PDT)	Chambal R.	0	0
Kunwari R.		0	0	3
Sindh R.		2	0	2
Betwa R.		13	63	76
Ken R.		0	9	9

Floodplain fine (FF)			
Sample name	>125 mm	<125 mm	Total no of charcoal-FF
Aglar R.	51	199	250
Naro R.	0	67	67
Bhim R.	0	3	3
Amlawa R.	0	0	0
Tons R.	194	113	307
Giri B.	44	1687	1731
Asan R.	0	6	6
Bata R.	62	132	193
SDT 1	0	3	3
SDT 2	2	10	12
SDT 3	0	186	186
SDT 4	0	0	0
SDT 5	12	4	16
Chambal R.	1	67	68
Kunwari R.	0	0	0
Sindh R.	0	0	0
Betwa R.	3	1	4
Ken R.	0	1	1

Table 1: Microscopic charcoal count (>125 μm and <125 μm) in the bedload and the floodplain (per volume of sediments) deposits of the tributaries draining Yamuna sub-basin.